

ISic0114

I.Sicily inscription 0114

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

plaque

Editor

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Principal Contributor

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Autopsy

Photographed 2018-07-10

Last Change

2020-12-10 - Jonathan Prag edited file from publication and photograph

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Original details of discovery not recorded; first attested in Termini

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico Baldassare Romano, inventory 102

Physical Description

A thick, pinkish limestone plaque, intact on all sides but with the face damaged on the left, upper and right edges (later re-working?), and the lower right corner

Dimensions

Height 21 cm

Width 29.5 cm

Depth 9 cm

Layout

Three lines of Latin text, approximately centred and with a vacat below

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Neat thinly cut letters mostly without substantial serifs/terminations to the strokes. Letters are somewhat irregular both in height and width. A has horizontal bar which does not fully intersect the diagonals; B has rounded eyes, not closed, and the upper is smaller; E has equal horizontal strokes; G has vertical tail stroke; O is variable in dimensions; P has rounded open head; R is lcosd, with full tail. Small triangular interpunct in line 1.

Letter heights:

Line 1-3: 32-40 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not recorded mm

Text

1. P(ublio) · Antonio P(ublio) [(i)bert(o)]
2. Psorioni
3. ergolabo

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation (en)

To Publius Antonius Psorion, (freedman?) of Publius, a contractor.

Commentary

The term 'ergolabus', a transliteration of the Greek ἐργόλαβος is possibly unique in Latin (instead of redemptor); the Greek term is occasionally attested.

Digital identifiers:

TM 285317

EDR 127537

EDCS 22100064

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-11): ISic0114. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4316591>

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